

INCORPORATION OF SOLE AND AMENDED AGRO-INDUSTRIAL BIOMASS FOR SOIL BULK DENSITY AND POROSITY IMPROVEMENT, ROOT GROWTH AND POD YIELD OF OKRA
(*Abelmoschus esculentum Moench L*)

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ABSTRACT

An investigation was carried out in Akure, Nigeria on the effect of sole and fortified agro-industrial biomass for improving soil bulk density and porosity improvement, root growth and pod yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentum L*)

The 20 organic fertilizer treatments were compared to chemical fertilizers (NPK 15-15-15 fertilizer) and a control (no fertilizer; no manure), replicated four times and arranged in a randomized complete block design.

The results showed that the application of 6/ha of agro-industrial biomass in sole forms or fortified with goat, pig and poultry manure increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) the soil porosity, root growth and pod yield of okra compared to the control treatment. The soil bulk density was also reduced significantly compared to the control treatment.

The amended *woodash*, *spentgrain*, *cocoa husk*, *ricebran* and sawdust with pig, goat and poultry manure reduced the soil bulk density values more than their ordinary forms. The NPK fertilizer and the control plots had relatively high bulk density and low porosity values.

Spentgrain applied sole or amended with manure most reduced the soil bulk density followed by *woodash*, *cocoa husk*, *ricebran* and sawdust respectively. This explained why the *spentgrain* (sole and amended forms) treatments had the best soil porosity, root growth and pod yield of okra compared to others.

The linear correlation “r” values between root length and pod yield of 2 okra were 0.40, 0.45, 0.57 and 0.68 at 1% level for crop 1, 2, 3, and 4 respectively showing that it is an important factor in the determination of okra pod weight.

Spentgrain applied sole or amended with animal manure was very useful in improving soil physical properties of a lowly fertile humid soils for sustainable agriculture.

KEYWORDS: Sole and amended agro industrial biomass, bulk density, porosity, root growth, pod yield and okra

INTRODUCTION

The physical resistance of the soil to the growth of crop seedlings and yield at different stages is an important factor in crop production particularly getting the right population density and development to maturity.

Aina *et al* (1985) reported that soil parameters known to affect the mechanical impedance included soil texture, bulk density and moisture content. The effect of soil compaction which commonly results from cultural practices such as continuous land clearing and tillage practices expose soils to deterioration of its organic matter and loss of essential nutrients for crop growth. Impedance to crop seedlings growth increases with soil bulk density.

Aina (1979) reported that as a result of diminished soil organic matter during a ten year continuous cultivation of an Iwo soil S. W. Nigeria, there was a considerable reduction in soil aggregation, porosity, hydraulic conductivity and increased bulk density. The ultimate consequence was decline in soil fertility.

Obi and Ofoduru (1997) reported that the use of mineral fertilizers such as NPK, Urea and Ammonium sulphate led to degradation of physical qualities of soils caused by low organic matter levels. This was supported by Zake (1973) who stated that a single heavy dose of soluble fertilizers might not work in the low activity clay soils, and they required an organic matter to impart appropriate chemical, physical and biological properties.

Although, the effects of bulk density and soil moisture regime on soil compaction and crop growth have been reported for some Nigerian soils (*Ultisol and Oxisols*) especially from the approach of tillage practice. (Ojeniyi, 1985 and, Lal, and Maurya, 1979). However, there is scarcity of research information on the use of agro-industrial biomass such as cocoa hush, *woodash*, sawdust, *ricebran* and *spentgrain* (brewery waste) applied in sole or amended with goat, pig and poultry manures for reducing soil bulk density, increasing porosity, root development and yield of okra.

Therefore, the objectives are to determine the influence of agro-industrial wastes (Sole and amended forms) for soil bulk density and porosity improvement, root development and pod yield of okra (*Abelmoschus esculentum Moench L.*).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiments were carried out at Akure (7 N¹, 5¹10 E) in the rain forest zone of Nigeria in 1998 and 1999 on the same site. The soil is a sandy loam, skeletal, *kaolinitic, isohyperthermic oxic paleustaff (Alfisol)* or *ferric Luvisol* (FAO). The annual rainfall is 1300mm, a temperature of 70 F and relative humidity of 80%.

Determination of soil physical properties before planting

The physical properties of soils on the site were determined before field experiments. The soil bulk density (g/cm) was determined by steel core method. Ojeniyi (1985). The bulk density was calculated from the mass of the soil and the displaced volume of the water through the rate of *upthrust*.

The % porosity was calculated from the values of bulk density. The mechanical analysis of the soil was done by the hydrometer method. Bouyous (1951).

Collection, Processing and Chemical analysis of the organic materials.

The goat, pig and poultry manures were collected from the livestock section of Federal College of Agriculture, Akure. The *woodash*, cocoa pod husk and *ricebran* were collected from the cassava processing unit, cocoa plantations and rice mill at Federal College of Agriculture, Akure. The *spentgrain* and sawdust were collected from international Breweries Plc, Ilesa, Osun State, Nigeria and nearby sawmill industry in Akure respectively.

The organic materials were processed to allow decomposition. The dried cocoa pod husk was ground using hammer mill, *woodash* was sieved to remove burnt charcoal and pebbles. The *spentgrain*, *ricebran* and *cocoa husk* were each partially composted separately. The pig, goat and poultry manures were stacked individually to allow quick mineralisation processes.

The processed forms of the organic materials were analysed. The nutrient contents in the organic materials were determined using wet digestion method based on 25-5-5ml of HNO₃-H₂SO₄-HClO₄ acids. The filtrates collected, were evaluated for the C, N, P, K, Ca, Mg and Na contents and micronutrients (AOAC, 1970).

Field Experiment

The land was cleared, ploughed and harrowed. The soil was under arable crops for 10 years. The four field experiments were conducted on the early and late crops in 1998 and 1999 at the same site and each experiment spanned for four months.

Twenty organic fertilizer treatments, sole or amended were applied to each crop of okra, a reference treatment NPK 15-15-15 fertilizer (400kg/ha) and the control treatment (no manure, no fertilizer).

The five agro-industrial biomass were *woodash*, ground cocoa husk, *ricebran*, *spentgrain* (sorghum based brewery waste) and sawdust. The materials were applied sole at 6tha and each plant residues was combined with goat, pig and poultry manure at the rate of 3tha each.

The 22 treatments were replicated four times on each of the four consecutive okra crops and arranged in a randomized complete block design while the size of each of the plots was 4m x 4m (16m²)

The sole and amended residues were incorporated into the soil ten days before planting okra seeds using garden fork to allow easy decomposition. Four seeds of early maturing okra variety (NHAe-47-4) were planted per hole of 2cm deep at a spacing of 60x30cm. Germination took place five days planting and later thinned to one plant per stand.

The plots were manually weeded thrice starting from the second, fifth and seventh weeks after planting. The insect pests were controlled by spraying *vetox* 85 at the rate of 28g a.i in 9Lt of water starting from second week after planting (WAP).

Harvest of the mature pods started at 40 days after planting and it continued at every four days interval until *senescence*. The total weight of harvested pods were determined (kg/ha) and at the end of each experiment, all the okra plants were uprooted and seminal root lengths were determined.

Soil Physical properties after the experiment

At end of each experiment on okra, soil bulk density and % porosity were determined for each treatment plot as described earlier.

Statistical analysis of the data

The data recorded for the bulk density, % porosity, root length and yields of four crops of okra were analysed using ANOVA F-test and their means were separated using the Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at 5% level. Simple linear correlations relationship between the soil bulk density, root length and yield of okra were also presented.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Determination of physical properties before planting

The data on the soil physical properties such as soil bulk density, % porosity, % sand, silt and clay were presented in Table 1. The soils used for the cultivation of okra have sandy loam texture with high proportion of sand and this would adversely affect the growth of crops because of probable low water and nutrient retention capacities. Hence, relatively poor growth of okra on soils not treated with organic industrial biomass.

The high soil bulk density values affected the soil porosity, root growth and yield of okra in the control treatment as well as contributing to low organic matter status of the soils. This finding agreed with that of

Ojeniyi, 1985 who reported that there was a strong relationship between soil bulk density and organic matter status in a soil.

Analysis of the chemical composition for agro-industrial biomass

Table 2 presents the chemical composition of the agro-industrial biomass used for the cultivation of okra. The agro-industrial biomass such as *woodash*, *ricebran*, *cocoa husk*, *spentgrain* and sawdust have lower values of plant nutrients such as N and P compared to the poultry, pig and goat manure, hence, they have high C/N ratio and are expected to decompose more slowly. Thus, a combination of the animal manure and plant residues are expected to improve their effectiveness in reducing soil bulk density values, increased soil porosity, root growth and yield of okra.

Ricebran and sawdust have relatively high C:N compared with *cocoa husk*, *woodash* and *spentgrain*, therefore, they are expected to be less efficient in returning plant nutrients and organic matter for the reduction in soil bulk density, improved root growth and yield of okra.

Effect of agro-industrial biomass on the soil bulk density, porosity, root growth and yield of okra.

The data on the soil bulk density values (Table 3), soil porosity (Table 4), root growth (Table 5) and pod weight of okra (Table 6) under the different agro-industrial biomass were presented. The sole and amended agro-industrial biomass increased significantly ($P < 0.05$) the porosity, root growth and pod weight of okra compared to the control treatments for the four crops of okra.

Soil bulk density was reduced with each addition of manure from the first to fourth crop of okra. Amendment of *woodash*, *spentgrain*, *cocoa husk*, *ricebran* and sawdust with animal manure reduced the soil bulk density values more than their ordinary forms. The NPK fertilizer and the control plots had relatively high bulk density values. *Spentgrain* applied sole or amended with manure most reduced the soil bulk density compared with *woodash*, *cocoa husk*, *ricebran* and sawdust.

Although, the *spentgrain* had the least C,N,P,Ca,Mg, Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn status compared to *cocoa husk* and *woodash*, it most reduced the bulk density out of the five agro-industrial biomass through its relatively low density and probable relatively high porosity. The combination of its better fertility status and best porosity would have enhanced root growth and yield of okra.

The reduction in soil bulk density by application of *spentgrain* should have positively influenced other soil physical properties such as aeration and water infiltration, thereby enhancing root growth, hence, it was discovered that the *spentgrain* most improved the growth of okra compared to others.

This finding is significant considering the fact that soil bulk density is an important soil parameter in crop production. Aina (1979) reported that as a result of diminished soil organic matter during a ten years continuous cultivation of an Iwo soil in S.W. Nigeria, there was a considerable increase in soil bulk density and serious reduction in soil aggregation, porosity and hydraulic conductivity. The ultimate consequence was decline in soil fertility, hence, low root growth, high bulk density and low yield of okra under control treatment.

Obi and Ofoduru (1997) also reported that the continuous use of NPK fertilizer in soil would lead to degradation of physical properties of soils especially bulk density caused by low organic matter levels and this could be responsible for the increased values of soil bulk density in NPK fertilized soils compared to the sole and amended agro-industrial biomass.

The best yield of okra associated with the use of *spentgrain* is also attributable to its mostly reduced soil bulk density out of all the agro-industrial biomass. This is corroborated by the fact that okra grown on *spentgrain* manured soil had the longest roots and the enhancement of soil structural condition might have improved root growth, nutrient and water uptake. The improvement of soil physical condition by applied *spentgrain* is consistent with the assertion of Woome and Muchena (1993) that continuous productivity of

tropical soils is associated with maintenance and improvement of soil physical characteristics which can be further improved by the use of organic fertilizers.

RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

Agro-industrial biomass such as *woodash*, cocoa husk and *spentgrain* when used ordinarily or fortified with pig, goat and poultry manure are very effective sources of improving the soil porosity, root development and pod weight of okra and reduced bulk density. Sawdust and *ricebran* were less effective.

It is, therefore, recommended that sole and fortified agro-industrial biomass such as *woodash*, *spentgrain* and cocoa husk applied at 6t/ha are very useful organic fertilizers for improving soil porosity, root development and pod weight of okra and reduced soil bulk density. The use of sole and amended *spentgrain* was particularly the best in improving soil porosity, root growth and pod yield of okra and reduced soil bulk density.

This recommendation is very important because continuous use of inorganic fertilizers for soil fertility improvement is accompanied by destruction of soil physical properties, besides, such fertilizers are very expensive and scarce beyond the scope of poor resources farmers who are still the major producers of food in tropical countries of Africa, Asia and so forth.

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Table 1: Soil Physical Properties Before Planting of Okra

S/N	SOIL PROPERTIES	OKRA CROP
1.	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	1.60
2.	Total Porosity (%)	41.81
3.	Texture	
4.	Sand (%)	80.60
5.	Silt (%)	15.60
6.	Clay	3.80
	Textural Class	Sandy Loam
	Local Soil Classification	Akure Soil Series
	USDA Soil Classification	Alfisol

Table 2 : Chemical Composition of the organic materials used for the experiment

Treatments	C	N	C:N	P	Ca	K	Mg	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn
Cocoa husk	16.00	1.44	11.11	100	9.34	20.60	7.10	50.40	8.40	0.55	1.77
Woodash	18.00	1.53	11.80	86.00	9.40	23.00	8.50	65.50	11.90	0.66	1.88
Spentgrain	100.00	0.78	12.80	56.00	0.13	7.90	3.10	3.40	0.99	0.10	0.70
Ricebran +	14.00	0.60	23.30	76.00	0.12	7.90	1.80	6.30	1.80	0.18	0.50
Sawdust +	8.00	0.42	19.00	110.00	0.10	5.10	1.30	4.00	1.70	0.16	0.40
Poultry manure	30.00	4.33	6.93	385.00	3.20	9.72	4.10	37.85	1.66	0.15	1.26
Goat manure	20.00	2.52	7.93	167.50	2.90	9.97	4.50	34.50	1.60	0.16	1.30
Pig manure	25.00	3.72	6.72	312.00	3.10	14.45	4.80	34.00	1.62	0.17	1.34

+ Undergo decomposition for six weeks before analysis.

TABLE 3: The effect of plant residues plus manure on soil bulk density (g/cm^3) under the four crop of Okra

S/N	TREATMENTS	1 ST	2 ND	3 RD	4 TH	5 TH
1.	Control (No fertilizer)	1.68n	1.68d	1.66r	1.67p	1.67l
2.	NPK 15-15-15	1.61m	1.62n	1.59q	1.60o	1.61k
3.	Wood Ash (Sole)	1.54ij	1.48gh	1.43hi	1.35q	1.45de
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	1.52gh	1.45de	1.38d	1.33ef	1.42cd
5.	Wood Ash + pig Dung	1.50ef	1.46ef	1.36c	1.31d	1.41c
6.	Wood Ash + poultry Manure	1.49de	1.44cd	1.39de	1.32de	1.41c
7.	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	1.53hi	1.50l	1.46k	1.41l	1.48fg
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	1.51fg	1.48gh	1.44ij	1.40hi	1.46ef
9.	Cocoa Husk + pig Dung	1.49de	1.47fg	1.42gh	1.39h	1.44d
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry Manure	1.48cd	1.46ef	1.41fg	1.40hi	1.44d
11.	Rice Bran (Sole)	1.56kl	1.53kl	1.51op	1.48n	1.52j
12.	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	1.54ij	1.51ij	1.49mn	1.45lm	1.50hi
13.	Rice Bran + pig Dung	1.53hi	1.51ij	1.48lm	1.42j	1.49gh
14.	Rice Bran + poultry Manure	1.51fg	1.50l	1.47kl	1.45lm	1.47f
15.	Spent Grain (Sole)	1.48cd	1.44cd	1.40ef	1.31d	1.41c
16.	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	1.46b	1.42b	1.36c	1.29bc	1.38h
17.	Spent Grain + pig Dung	1.47bc	1.43bc	1.32a	1.28b	1.38b
18.	Spent Grain + poultry Manure	1.43a	1.39a	1.34b	1.26a	1.36a
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	1.55jk	1.54lm	1.50no	1.48n	1.52j
20.	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	1.53hi	1.52jk	1.49mn	1.43jk	1.49gh
21.	Saw Dust + pig Dung	1.53gh	1.51ij	1.47kl	1.44kl	1.49gh
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry Manure	1.54ij	1.50l	1.48lm	1.45lm	1.49gh

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

Table 4: The effect of agro-industrial biomass on % soil porosity under the four crops of Okra.

S/N	Treatments	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Mean
1.	Control (No fertilizer)	39.00a	39.00a	39.64a	39.27a	39.23a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	41.46b	41.09b	42.18b	41.82b	41.64b
3.	Wood Ash (sole)	33.00c	46.18d	48.00gh	50.91i	47.27f
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	44.73cd	47.27f	49.82jk	51.64j	48.37h
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	45.46de	46.91ef	50.55l	52.36k	48.82i
6.	Wood Ash + Poultry Manure	45.82e	47.64fg	49.46ij	52.00jk	48.73hi
7.	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	44.36cd	45.46de	46.91f	48.73f	46.37e
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	45.09d	46.18d	47.64g	49.09fg	47.00f
9.	Cocoa Husk + pig Dung	45.82e	46.55e	48.36h	49.46gh	47.55fg
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry Dung	46.18d	46.91ef	48.73hi	49.09fg	47.73g
11.	Rice Bran (Sole)	43.27c	44.36c	45.09c	46.18c	44.73c
12.	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	44.00c	45.09d	45.82d	47.27d	45.55d
13.	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	44.36cd	45.09d	46.18e	48.36ef	46.00e
14.	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	45.09d	45.46de	46.55ef	47.27d	46.09e
15.	Spent Grain (Sole)	46.18ef	47.64fy	49.09i	52.36k	48.82i
16.	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	46.91fg	48.36gh	50.55l	53.09l	49.73j
17.	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	46.55f	48.00g	52.00n	53.46lm	50.00j
18.	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	48.00h	49.46i	51.27m	54.18n	50.73k
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	43.64c	44.00c	45.46cd	46.18c	44.82c
20.	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	44.36cd	44.73cd	45.82d	49.00e	45.73d
21.	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	44.73cd	45.09d	46.55ef	47.64de	46.00e
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	44.00c	45.46de	46.18e	47.27d	45.73d

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.

Table 5: The effects of plant residues plus manure on the root length (cm) under four crops of Okra.

S/N.	Treatment	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Mean
1.	Control (No fertilizer)	8.52a	8.46a	8.47a	8.65a	8.53a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	28.652m	29.608j	31.136h	56.788ij	30.30n
3.	Wood Ash (Sole)	15.54ef	23.07f	29.877g	29.914e	24.60fg
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	19.512h	29.134j	37.691m	38.042j	31.09op
5.	Wood Ash + pig Dung	17.666g	26.464h	34.309l	34.446hi	28.24hl
6.	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	21.472jk	32.244l	41.759o	41.956l	34.36r
7.	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	12.536c	18.804c	24.445c	24.476cd	20.06d
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	15.044e	22.652e	29.551g	29.492c	24.18f
9.	Cocoa Husk + pig Dung	16.376f	23.936f	31.384h	31.242f	25.73h
10.	Cocoa Husk + Poultry manure	22.694	31.196	41.582o	41.532l	34.25r
11.	Rice Bran (Sole)	11.99bc	18.206c	23.474b	23.712c	19.35c
12.	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	13.74d	20.546d	26.436d	26.148d	21.72e
13.	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	16.28f	25.085hi	32.288i	32.648g	26.78j
14.	Rice Bran + Poultry manure	21.86k	24.17g	28.376f	29.462e	25.97h
15.	Spent Grain (Sole)	17.452g	26.162i	34.029j	34.03hi	27.92k
16.	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	20.248j	30.42k	38.87n	39.562k	32.28q
17.	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	19.56h	29.354j	36.092m	38.558j	30.89no
18.	Spent Grain + poultry manure	22.06l	33.14m	43.044p	38.75jk	34.25r
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	10.98b	16.11b	27.73e	21.216b	15.26b
20.	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	16.50f	24.426g	31.474h	31.79f	26.05hi
21.	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	17.22g	27.18l	34.298k	33.694h	28.10kl
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	18.28h	27.33i	35.492lm	35.548l	29.16m

Treatment means within each group of column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level

Table 6: The effect of plant residues plus manure on fresh pod weight of Okra (gross plot) under four crops of Okra in kg/hectare.

S/N.	Treatment	1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	Mean
1.	Control (no fertilizer)	46.81a	46.80a	46.70a	46.85a	46.78a
2.	NPK 15-15-15	536.40k	801.63k	1335.42h	1469.75h	704.80f
3.	Wood Ash (Sole)	254.50d	383.75cd	1117.76d	1102.01d	464.51c
4.	Wood Ash + Goat Dung	548.75kl	823.97l	22.13.00l	2201.10l	1446.71m
5.	Wood Ash + Pig Dung	571.40n	853.31m	24.03.39n	2390.74n	957.03l
6.	Wood Ash + Poultry manure	630.98p	1095.72q	2692.93op	2672.33o	1772.99p
7.	Cocoa Husk (Sole)	275.95f	414.76e	1183.43f	1169.55e	760.92g
8.	Cocoa Husk + Goat Dung	606.19o	777.47j	2257.48m	2240.11m	1470.31mn
9.	Cocoa Husk + Pig Dung	594.23n	892.58mn	2614.53o	2590.74j	1673.02o
10.	Cocoa Husk + poultry manure	641.00q	962.50n	3003.66p	2979.98p	1896.79q
11.	Rice Bran (Sole)	214.36c	324.09c	920.88b	900.88b	590.05d
12.	Rice Bran + Goat Dung	475.16j	714.04ij	2035.03jk	2013.53j	1309.44j
13.	Rice Bran + Pig Dung	533.74k	838.88lm	2076.77k	2054.11k	1375.88l
14.	Rice Bran + poultry manure	558.75l	704.06l	2026.54j	1999.89l	1322.31jk
15.	Spent Grain (Sole)	386.58l	579.37h	2268.62m	2260.15mn	1373.68l
16.	Spent Grain + Goat Dung	654.33r	981.30o	3113.30q	3092.28q	1760.30r
17.	Spent Grain + Pig Dung	686.53s	1026.11op	3724.21r	3632.68r	2267.38s
18.	Spent Grain + Poultry manure	716.41t	1074.64p	4076.52s	4032.23s	2474.75t
19.	Saw Dust (Sole)	180.62b	271.65b	996.45c	978.78c	606.88de
20.	Saw Dust + Goat Dung	260.72e	388.55d	1170.33e	1495.18h	828.70h
21.	Saw Dust + Pig Dung	297.23g	447.22f	1319.13g	1299.55f	210.19b
22.	Saw Dust + Poultry manure	341.335h	541.33g	1493.54l	1437.60g	953.45l
	Mean (X)	471.44	704.77	2135.38	2127.69	

Treatment means within each group or column followed by the same letters are not significantly different from each other using DMRT at 5% level.